

European Data Union Strategy: Call for Evidence

Contribution of the Centre for Internet and Society CNRS, Open Knowledge Estonia, Open Knowledge Finland, Open Knowledge Sweden and Open Knowledge Foundation

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Executive Summary: This document presents the joint response of contributors to the public consultation on '[A European Data Union Strategy](#)'. To create a more coherent and effective legal framework, we propose the following 5 pillars as foundations for the strategy:

1. Strengthen the reuse of public sector information, by clarifying certain regulatory instruments such as the Open Data Directive, the High-Value Datasets Implementing Regulation, and the Data Governance Act.
2. Improve open data portals, by focussing on consistent metadata standards and inclusion of feedback loops.
3. Encourage sustainable reuse of data, by funding research on sustainable business models for new data sharing and reuse frameworks as well as environmental assessments of data sharing and reuse initiatives.
4. Encourage use of open standards, protocols and softwares for open data as well as data reuse.
5. Stimulate investment in public data infrastructures.

Introduction

The authors and contributors of this document welcome the public consultation by the European Commission on ‘[A European Data Union Strategy](#)’ (Data Union Strategy), which aims to streamline existing data rules and boost availability of high-quality data, potentially creating a simplified, clearer, and more coherent legal framework and infrastructure for businesses and administrations to share data more seamlessly and at scale, while still upholding high privacy and security standards.

The Data Union Strategy presents an important opportunity for the European Commission to disseminate a clear stance and roadmap on data sharing to boost European digital sovereignty as well as the public interest. While there are various regulatory instruments, particularly those stemming from the [Data Strategy of 2020](#), it is also important to anticipate and resolve incompatibilities. Further, the Data Union Strategy also provides the gateway to focus on sustainability aspects of data sharing infrastructures - particularly financial and environmental sustainability as also maintenance of data sharing infrastructures, to ensure that EU initiatives such as [data intermediaries](#), [data altruism](#) and the [common European data spaces](#) reduce the control that Big Tech exercise over data flows.

Accordingly, we propose 5 pillars for the Data Union Strategy.

Pillar 1: Strengthening reuse of Public Sector Information

The 2019 Open Data Directive combined with Chapter II of the Data Governance Act enables reuse of public sector information (PSI) to a widest possible extent. A combined reading of both legal instruments reveal a three-tiered structure:

- High-value datasets - widest reuse
Six thematic categories of datasets which are to be made freely available by public administrations on national open data portals and under open licenses, in machine-readable format, and accessible through both application programming interfaces (APIs) and bulk downloads.
- Other public sector information covered under the scope of the 2019 Open Data Directive - open government data
PSI is encouraged to be made available as open by design and default for both commercial and non-commercial use. Where possible, such data is to be made available “by electronic means in formats that are open, machine-readable, accessible, findable and reusable, together with their metadata.” In most cases, public administrations can charge marginal costs. Publicly-funded research data is also encouraged to be made open.
- Difficult categories of public sector information - conditional reuse

PSI that are protected on grounds of commercial confidentiality, statistical confidentiality, third party intellectual property rights, or personal data protection, do not fall within the scope of the Open Data Directive. But, pursuant to Chapter II of the Data Governance Act, such ‘difficult’ categories of data can be available for reuse subject to certain conditions - such as anonymization in the case of personal data, or access and reuse within a secure processing environment, and in all cases, with due regard for personal data protection rules under the GDPR. Public administrations can charge fees for reuse, provided such fees are transparent, non-discriminatory, proportionate and objectively justified, and do not restrict competition.

To ensure compatibility between the Open Data Directive and the Data Governance Act, as also to ensure that the three-tiered structure described above enables the realisation of wide social and economic value from public sector information, we propose two regulatory changes:

Pillar 1(A): The list of high-value datasets should be expanded.

At present, the 6 thematic categories of high-value datasets are geospatial, earth observation and environment, meteorological data, statistical data, company and company ownership data, and mobility. As suggested by [open data practitioners](#), the category of high-value datasets should be expanded to include other categories of data that also have high citizen demand as well as high potential for impact in terms of both economic value generation as well as citizen participation and accountability. This includes data on public finance, public procurement, public health, as well as language data given its growing importance for participatory Generative AI development. Further, the European open data portal as well as national open data portals could include a feedback loop by which public feedback on high-value datasets can be provided.

While these types of data can still be accessed by way of freedom of information requests, they must be made available automatically as open datasets, rather than be subject to a request-based data access mechanism. This can also significantly boost data availability and data quality for AI development, particularly AI applications in critical domains such as public administration and climate action.

Pillar 1(B): The overlap between the Open Data Directive and Chapter II of the Data Governance Act should be clarified.

The Data Governance Act assumes that ‘difficult’ categories of public sector information are neatly and necessarily separable from public sector information covered under the Open Data Directive. In reality, [this distinction is not so clear](#). Public administrations can, for example, redact documents containing personal data or commercially confidential information, and release the redacted documents as open data under the Open Data Directive. Some member

states such as [France](#) have included such obligations in their national transposition of the Open Data Directive. It logically follows that Article 3(1) of the Data Governance Act should apply to the redacted data elements in these redacted documents.

However, Article 5(3) of the Data Governance Act assumes that documents as a whole are outside the scope of the Open Data Directive, and therefore can be made conditionally available at the discretion of public administrations.

This creates confusion as well as potential for fragmentation within EU member states, as it leads to a situation where member states can reduce the scope of the Open Data Directive as transposed into their national law, and instead enable conditional access to public sector information under the framework set out in Chapter II of the Data Governance Act.

As a result, the scope of Chapter II of the Data Governance Act should be clarified. It could be clarified/amended to mean **data elements** within documents held by public sector bodies that are commercially confidential, statistically confidential, are protected by third party intellectual property rights or protected by personal data. In doing so, the Data Governance Act can clarify that, to the extent possible, redacted documents as a whole should fall within the scope of the Open Data Directive, while access to the specific redacted data elements within the redacted documents can be obtained via the Data Governance Act.

Pillar 2: Improving usability of open data portals

To ensure findability and usability of PSI, Member States of the European Union should signal their commitment to adoption of metadata standards for PSI released pursuant to national transposition of the Open Data Directive. Specialised standards for PSI developed using an open collaborative process, such as [DCAT-AP](#), should be adopted at scale. Further, such PSI should also be connected to the European Union's open data portal - <https://data.europa.eu/en>. This will boost the discoverability of national PSI.

Feedback loops to ensure co-creation of PSI is also necessary. In particular, feedback loops by which inaccuracies in open datasets as well as missing data can be flagged by users is important. Such feedback loops can be integrated into national open data portals, through the use of public discussion boards as in the case of [France's national open data portal](#).

Pillar 3: Encouraging sustainable data reuse

As a horizontal framework, the Data Governance Act creates many routes for reuse of public sector information, personal data as well as privately-held data. In addition to Chapter II of the Data Governance Act for conditional reuse of 'difficult' categories of public sector information, the Data Governance Act also identifies data intermediaries and data altruism organisations as

two other routes by which personal data and privately-held data can be shared by data holders with data users.

Here, the Data Union Strategy can highlight the importance of sustainability. For instance, with regard to data intermediaries, economic sustainability needs to be explored more, as noted in a [recent report of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre](#) as well. Data intermediaries need to build clear value propositions as well as generate short and long-term revenue streams while respecting neutrality provisions under the Data Governance Act. In other words, data intermediaries need to develop business models that do not depend on data-driven services generated from the data that are shared through the data intermediaries. At the same time, value propositions of data intermediaries based solely on increasing individual control over data or ensuring financial payment in exchange for personal data may not always result in welfare-maximisation.

Business models that are rooted in certain forms of reciprocity could provide beneficial, to ensure that the regulatory recognition of data intermediaries results in the creation of new market players in the data economy beyond Big Tech platforms. In this regard, the European Commission can facilitate more financing for empirical research on such business models.

Further, for both data intermediaries as well as data altruism organisations, the European Commission can also facilitate research into the use of alternative licensing / contractual arrangements between data holders and data users. This is particularly relevant for the creation of datasets for AI training, to ensure availability of high-quality data while also respecting the preferences of communities who generate this data and/or who steward this data. Often, openly licensed content or donated data are used to train AI models, but there is little to value given back to the maintenance of the datasets and data infrastructure, nor the ability of the data communities to participate in the AI development. As a result, there is also a push towards more enclosure. Alternative licenses encode new obligations for reciprocity, such as payment of fees by data users that is routed towards maintenance of the dataset. Some examples of such alternative licenses are the [Open Data Commons License](#), the [UsageRights License](#), the [Nwulite Obodo License](#) and the [Feminist Peer Production License](#). Another emerging initiative led by Creative Commons is the use of [preference signals](#) to create a new social contract for machine reuse of open web data. Further, the use of legal structures like data trusts to monitor compliance with these licenses should also be studied more, which can also be facilitated through European research financing.

And finally, the environmental impact of certain data sharing infrastructures must also be considered. For instance, while blockchain based data sharing technologies do allow for more transparency, they also carry a heavy environmental footprint. As a result, the Data Union Strategy should also encourage environmental impact assessments for data intermediation and data altruism initiatives.

Pillar 4: Open standards, protocols, APIs, and softwares

To boost competition, limit vendor lock-ins and ensure European digital sovereignty, openness must be a central feature of the Data Union Strategy. Open standards to ensure semantic interoperability of datasets, open protocols and APIs to facilitate data transfers, and open source software-based technologies for data analysis and data storage can create a level playing field for the European data economy, as well as limit reliance on Big Tech cloud infrastructures. The Data Union Strategy should signal a strong preference for such open components where feasible, with due regard for privacy and security.

Low-tech open tools such as the Open Knowledge Foundation's [Open Data Editor](#) are also crucial to ensure that low to medium resource organisations with limited resources for technical skill development can also participate in the creation and maintenance of open datasets. To this extent, the European Commission can encourage member states to collaborate closely with providers of such tools as well build public repositories of such tools.

Pillar 5: Stimulating investments in public data infrastructures

We support calls for the creation of an [EU Sovereign Tech Fund](#), to direct public investment into open technologies, particularly for dataset creation, storage and data sharing in the context of AI development. Such investment can significantly aid in creating an ecosystem of European open technologies that can compete with Big Tech AI companies. Such investment can also ensure maintenance of open technologies, which often relies on unpaid voluntary labour. Finally, such investment can also be a vehicle by which to infuse social and environmental justice into open technologies, by evaluating and monitoring the commitment of funding recipients to gender equality and environmental sustainability.

Conclusion:

The Data Union Strategy presents a crucial step forward, in ensuring European digital sovereignty, by outlining legal and institutional measures for sustainable reuse of data in the service of public interest. The pillars proposed in this document could serve as a few starting points towards this objective. We look forward to the final Data Union Strategy.

Contributing institutions

- **Centre for Internet and Society, CNRS**, <https://cis.cnrs.fr/>

The Center for Internet and Society (CIS) is a CNRS research center combining a research unit (UPR 2000) created in 2019, and the Internet, AI and Society (GDR 2091) Research Network, founded in 2020. At the intersection of sociology, law, history, economics, political science, information and communication sciences, computer and engineering sciences, the CIS intends to build independent and interdisciplinary research and expertise. The CIS' research endeavours to contribute to enlightening the major technical controversies and the definition of contemporary policies related to the digital, to the internet, and more broadly to informatics. As part of its activities, CIS is also a laboratory for the elaboration and promotion of good practices in digital technology for science (collaborative tools, digital methods of survey, analysis and visualization of data, communication strategy, participatory research).

- **Open Knowledge Foundation**, <https://okfn.org/en/>

Since 2004, the Open Knowledge Foundation (OKFN) has worked at the intersection of cutting-edge digital tools and a distributed network of communities and movements to serve the public interest with open knowledge. OKFN creates digital tools, equip people with skills, and expand digitally savvy networks that understand the transformative power of openness. Confronting the multi-complex challenges that the planet is facing today, OKFN is working for open knowledge to be a guiding principle in designing the infrastructures and organisations of the future, inspiring and guiding those who want to transform our digital and physical world by building a free, sustainable and inclusive future. OKFN also maintains and supports a global network of groups in more than 40 countries and counting.

- **Open Knowledge Estonia**, <https://okee.ee/>

Open Knowledge Estonia is a member of the Open Knowledge Network. The community was created from the desire of network members to put together their knowledge and experience in in order to promote the free movement of data and knowledge in society. Today, OKEE has become a broader promoter of data literacy and digital literacy and a champion of digital space and rights in Estonia.

- **Open Knowledge Finland**, <https://www.okf.fi/>

Open Knowledge Finland (OKFI) is a registered not-for-profit association and part of the Open Knowledge Network. The association was founded in 2012 and has members who present widely the Finnish field of Open Access to knowledge. The member base includes individuals, companies and other organizations. The association also manages a wide network of people and projects related to open knowledge.

- **Open Knowledge Sweden**, <https://okfn.se/>

Open Knowledge Sweden is a non-profit organisation founded in 2014, and is the official chapter from Sweden in the Open Knowledge Network. The key mission of the organisation is

to foster transparency, accountability and public participation, through the promotion of civic tech initiatives, open data, open knowledge, as well as by research and knowledge dissemination in the public, private and civic sectors.

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